

The inclined loop with exercises

Harald Schröder

2015

We view the inclined loop with the angle of inclination α . R is the radius of the loop and the radius of the belonging sphere, which helps for the following calculation. To the angles β, δ , see figure.

From the figure we obtain:

$$\sin \delta = \frac{Z}{K}$$

$Z =$ centrifugal force $K =$ gravitation

$$Z = \frac{mv^2}{R} \quad K = mg$$

$m =$ mass of the ball $v =$ velocity

with that:

$$\sin \delta = \frac{v_{min}^2}{Rg} \Rightarrow v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \sin \delta}$$

Now we must determine the angle δ . We use the spherical triangle with the right angle, β , α und δ .

The sine law of spherical trigonometry is applicable:

$$\frac{\sin \beta}{\sin 90^\circ} = \frac{\sin \delta}{\sin \alpha}$$

With $\sin 90^\circ = 1$ we get:

$$\sin \delta = \sin \beta \sin \alpha$$

Insertion:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \sin \beta \sin \alpha}$$

At the vertical loop, we count γ from above. Here β is counted from the lower part of the loop. It is valid $\gamma + \beta = 90^\circ$ that means $\sin \beta = \cos \gamma$. It follows:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \cos \gamma \sin \alpha}$$

At $\alpha = 90^\circ$ we have the special case (vertical loop). Then we obtain the known formula $v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \cos \gamma}$ of the vertical loop, see Schröder [2]. Another special case is the maximum height of the inclined loop ($\gamma = 0$):

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \sin \alpha}$$

At $\alpha = 0$, no velocity is needed to maintain **contact** with the loop. But the ball can still move downwards on the loop course.

It is clear that orbits on the upper half of the sphere are possible, too, but the ball needs a minimum velocity.

The frictionless case in the medium can be treated in the same way, if we insert instead of g , $\frac{g \cdot (\varphi_K - \varphi_F)}{\varphi_K} = g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right)$ (e.g. Budo [1] §16 p.85) in the equations. φ_F is the medium's density (liquid or gas) and φ_K is the body's density that is in balance.

reasons:

In this balance case, only gravitation and centrifugal force play a role. The centrifugal force is independent of the medium. In the orbit case, the centrifugal force is dependent only on r and v (we can see it in the derivation of the centrifugal force) but not upon the medium. The gravitational acceleration changes from g to $g \cdot \frac{\varphi_K - \varphi_F}{\varphi_K}$. Only with the gravitation is there a change. Because of this, we can insert $g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right)$ instead of g .

In the case $\varphi_F > \varphi_K$ the loop must be turned around.
instead of

then

Then the same equations are valid again.

We introduce the radius r of the small ball. If we take the barycenter of the small ball into consideration, then we must insert $R - r$ instead of R in the equations. We assume that the small ball has a (local) constant density.

Exercises:

1. A loop of 4m diameter is inclined with 35° . What minimum velocity is necessary for the ball to run through the point with the angle $\beta = 22^\circ$?
2. A loop of 10m diameter has a inclination of 66° . Which minimum velocity is necessary at the point with the angle $\gamma = 16^\circ$?
3. A loop with an 8m diameter is inclined by 57° . A point is run through with a minimum velocity of $3.5 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. Which position angle belongs to it?

4. The point at height angle $\gamma = 18^\circ$ can be run through with a minimum velocity of $1.5 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. The loop has an inclination of 34° . How big is the loop's radius?

5. The loop with an 30m diameter is inclined with 76° . With which minimum velocity must the highest point be run through?

6. The highest point is run through at a loop with 24m diameter with a minimum velocity of $6 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. At how many degrees is the loop inclined?

7. One at 12° inclined loop is in the water. This loop has a diameter of 3m. A white brass ball with the density $\varphi_K = 8.2 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ moves through the loop. How big is the minimum velocity at a height angle of 54° ?

Remark:

The density of water is at 20 degree Celsius $0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$.

8. A loop with an 6m diameter is in a large basin that is filled with water. The loop is inclined by 17° . A special point is run through with a minimum velocity of $0.9 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ by a copper ball. To which height angle does this point belong to?

Remark: The density of copper is $8.933 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$, to the density of water (see exercise 7).

Solutions of the exercises:

To exercise 1:

The loop has a radius of 2m. The inclination angle $\alpha = 35^\circ$ is known. Besides it is $\beta = 22^\circ$. v_{min} is searched. We use the following formula for the inclined loop:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot R \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

We obtain $v_{min} = 2.05 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

To exercise 2:

The loop radius is 5m. It is valid that $\alpha = 66^\circ$. We have the height angle $\gamma = 16^\circ$. With the equation

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot R \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

we get $v_{min} = 6.56 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

To exercise 3:

We take the following facts: $R = 4\text{m}$, $\alpha = 57^\circ$ and $v_{min} = 3.5 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. We search β and γ . From

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot R \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

follows:

$$v_{min}^2 = g \cdot R \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \sin \alpha$$

We obtain:

$$\sin \beta = \frac{v_{min}^2}{g \cdot R \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

As results follow $\beta = 21.9^\circ$ and $\gamma = 90^\circ \rightarrow \beta = 68.1^\circ$.

To exercise 4:

We have the height angle $\gamma = 18^\circ$ and $\alpha = 34^\circ$. The minimum velocity is $v_{min} = 1.5 \frac{m}{s}$. The loop radius R must be determined.

We use the equation:

$$v_{min}^2 = g \cdot R \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha$$

It follows:

$$R = \frac{v_{min}^2}{g \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

The calculation leads to $R = 0.43m$.

To exercise 5:

The loop radius R is 15m. It follows $\alpha = 76^\circ$. The minimum velocity at maximum height is searched.

For this case the formula

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot R \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

was derived. The insertion brings $v_{min} = 11.9 \frac{m}{s}$.

To exercise 6:

We have the loop radius $R = 12m$ and the minimum velocity $v_{min} = 6 \frac{m}{s}$ at maximum height. We search the inclination angle. We take:

$$v_{min}^2 = g \cdot R \cdot \sin \alpha$$

It follows:

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{v_{min}^2}{g \cdot R}$$

We obtain that $\alpha = 17.8^\circ$.

To exercise 7:

The inclined loop is in the water. The loop radius $R = 1.5\text{m}$, the height angle $\gamma = 54^\circ$ and $\alpha = 12^\circ$ are known. The density of white brass and of water at 20 degree Celsius are $\varphi_K = 8.2 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ respectively $\varphi_F = 0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$. We ask to v_{min} .

We apply the following formula:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot R \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

Because the loop is in the water, we must insert for the earth acceleration g the term $g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right)$. The complete equation is:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right) \cdot R \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

The calculation results in $v_{min} = 1.26 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

To exercise 8:

The inclined loop is in a water basin. The loop radius R is 3m. The known minimum velocity v_{min} is $0.9 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. $\alpha = 17^\circ$ is the inclination angle. It is valid that $\varphi_K = 8.933 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ and $\varphi_F = 0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$.

The height angle γ is searched. We use the same formula as in exercise 7:

$$v_{min}^2 = g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right) \cdot R \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot \sin \alpha$$

It follows:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_{min}^2}{g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_K}\right) \cdot R \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

We obtain $\gamma = 83.9^\circ$.

References

- [1] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980
- [2] Harald Schröder "The loop" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002